

SIMPLE SENTENCE PATTERNS THAT ARE COMPLICATED USING INPUT UNITS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7830336>

Abstract. In this article, simple sentence patterns complicated by Uzbek introductory units, introductory words, introductory compounds, and introductions are presented. Sentence patterns in both languages are compared and their similarities and differences are identified.

Keywords: simple sentence patterns, introductory units, introductory word, introductory compound, introduction, complicated simple sentence.

Introductory units express the speaker's subjective attitude and emotional feelings towards some parts of the sentence or the content of the whole sentence:

It is true, nature is a mother. (A. Mukhtor). – E + OK.

It is true, nature is a mother. – S + to be + M, + S + to be + (art)Noun.

Since there is an "intermediate third" between the introductory expanding word and the expanding sentence, they can be called a non-constructive part of the sentence.

In the structure of the sentence, there are many noun units that express the relation of subjective modality, which are directly related to this meaning in (Pm), although they do not enter into a grammatical relationship with the parts of the sentence and do not form a word combination:

1. Brother, will dad go to the parents' meeting today? - Dad will definitely go, maybe mom too.

2. It is true that a bad person should be punished, Saida said. The position of inputs in the construction of the sentence structure can be given as follows:

E	H	W	Pm	Introduction
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Words that are separated from the word group in the introductory task and are used only in the introductory task (*shekilli - probably, albatta - of course, demak - so, masalan - for example kabilar*), not separated from a certain word group, introduction words that can be used both as a function and as a part of a sentence (*birinchidan - the first, qisqasi - briefly, rost - really, aftidan - apparently, oxiri - eventually kabilar*). According to the structure of introductory units, there are 3 types: introductory clauses, introductory compounds, introductory sentences.

Introductory clauses consist of one word and are associated with a certain word group. Accordingly, the entrance sections are divided into the following types:

a) introductory clauses of the noun type: *chamasi - perhaps, taajjub - astonishment, odatda - usually, oxiri - eventually, nazdida - according to, baxtimizga - fortunatey, baxtga qarshi - unfortunately* and etc.

Baxtimizga, bugun yomg'ir yog'madi. – KB + H + E + K. *Fortunatey,*
it didn't rain today. – MW, + S + HV (not) + V + Adv.

b) pronoun-type introductory clauses: *menimcha - I think, seningcha - You think, uningcha - he thinks* and etc.

c) input adjectives of quality type: *so'zsiz - categorically, to'g'ri - correct, durust - nicely, qisqasi - briefly, tabiiy - naturally* and etc.

Qisqasi, hamma uyiga jo'nadi. – KB + E + H + K.

Briefly, everyone left home. – MW, + S + V + Adv.

d) numerals-type introductory clauses: *birinchidan* – first, *ikkinchidan* – second kabilar.

Birinchidan, kitobni o'qishingiz kerak. – KB + T + OK.

First, you must read the book. – MW + S + MV + V + (art) + O.

e) numerals-type introductory clauses *dastlab* – at first, *oxir- at last*, *nihoyat* – finally, *umuman* – generally, *asosan* – mainly, *aksincha* – on the contrary and etc.

Aksincha, siz undan uzr so'rashingiz kerak. – KB + E + T + K.

On the contrary, you should apologise to him. – MW, + S + MV + V + P + O.

f) verb-type introductory clauses: *kechirasiz* – sorry, *bundan chiqdiki* – so, and etc.
Kechirasiz, nima dedingiz? – KB + H + H + K?

Sorry, what was that again? – MW + S + to be + Pro + Adv.

The input compounds are in compound form and their structure is as follows:

a) demonstrative introductory conjunctions: *uning fikricha* – he thinks that, *buning ustiga* – in addition, *mening nazarimda* – I suppose and etc.

b) *Uning fikricha*, ertaga hamma qarindoshlarimiz kelarmish. – KB + H + H + E + K.

In his opinion, all our relatives will come tomorrow.

c) introductory compounds with adjectives: *bir tomondan* – on the one hand, *shu jumladan* – including and etc.

biz ham uning firriga qo'shildik. – KB + E + A + T + K.

Shu jumladan,
Including that we

agreed with him.

d) introductory phrases with adverb: *menga desa* – honestly speaking, *qisqasini aytsam* – in short, *to'g'risini aytganda* – To be honest and etc.

To'g'risini aytsam, men bulardan xabarsizman. – KB + E + T + OK.

To be honest, I don't know about them.

e) adverbial modifier input compounds: *qisqasini aytganda* – in short, *boshqacha aytganda* – in other words, *ochiq gapirganda* – speaking openly and etc.

Hech kimning, *ochiq gapirganda*, *birov bilan ishi yo'q edi*. – A + , KB, + T + E + K.

No one, frankly, had any business with anyone.

You are selfish, and judging by his frankness, you don't care about anyone but yourself.

f) introductory compounds with determiners and complements: *uning so'ziga qaraganda* – according to his word, *sening gapingga qaraganda* – from what you said and etc.

Ularga ishonmasligim kerakmi, *sening gapingga qaraganda*. – T + K + , KB.
Shouldn't I trust him, judging by your words?

Uning ochiq aytishicha, *jijonatda sening ham qo'ling bor*. – KB + T + A + K.

He openly said that you also had a hand in the crime.

g) Introductory conjunctions with determiner, adverbial modifier and adverb: *uning ochiq gapirishiga qaraganda* – as he speaks openly.

Sen xudbin ekansan, *uning ochiq gapirishiga qaraganda*, *o'zingdan boshqani o'yalamay qo'yipsan*. – E + K + , KB, + T + T + FK.

You are selfish, and judging by his frankness, you don't care about anyone but yourself.

Introductory sentences. These are in sentence form:

Qurbon ota aytmoqchi, *gullarni o'z ilmidan bahramand qildi (A.Q.)*. – KB + T + A + T + K.

Grandfather Qurbon wanted to say that he enjoyed the flowers from his knowledge.

Introductory structures represent the following: 1) Expresses the attitude of the speaker to the expressed opinion. To this albatta (of course), ehtimol, balki, shubhasiz, haqiqatan, darhaqiqat, baxtimizga (fortunately), afsus, essiz, so'zsiz, chamasi, shekilli, toleimizga, koshki, baxtga qarshi (unfortunately), muqarrar, ajab, to'g'risini aytganda, ochiq aytganda and etc.

These mean:

a) certainty or affirmation (such as certainly, undoubtedly, unquestionably, truly, inevitably):

Darhaqiqat, bugungi sayr umrbod esda qoladigan bo'ldi (J. A.). – KB, + A + E + H + K.

Indeed, today's trip was one to remember for life.

b) suspect (probably, perhaps, apparently):

Ehtimol, kelib qolar (So'zl.). – KB, + K.

Maybe, he will come

c) joy, satisfaction (fortunately, luckily, thankfully):

Xayriyat, bugun havo ochiq bo'ldi. - KB, + H + E + K.

Luckily, the weather is clear today.

d) regret, pity, surprise (unfortunately, regretfully, against happiness, surprisingly):

Eh, attang, shuncha mehnating ko'kka sovurilsa (Sh.R.). – KB, + H + E + K.

It is a pity if all your hard work goes to waste.

e) wish (maybe, wish):

Koshki, akasi Yo'lchi bo'lsa edi (O.). – KB, + E + K.

If only his brother was Yölchi.

2) Represents who the opinion belongs to. To this menimcha (I think), aytishlaricha (as they say), ma'lum bo'lishicha (as it turns out), uning so'ziga qaraganda (according to his words), uning qayd qilishicha (according to his notes), seningcha (according to you), nazarimda (in my opinion), sening gapingga qaraganda (according to your words) and etc:

Ernazar akaning aytishicha, bu yil saraton juda issiq boshlandi (I. R.). – KB, + H + E + H + K.

Brother Ernazar said that saraton started very hot this year.

3) Expresses the order of the thought being expressed. Birinchidan (Firstly), ikkinchidan (secondly), avvalo, nihoyat (at last), oxiri (finally) and etc: *Nihoyat, go'zal kunlarning birida zabardast odam bilan qudratli mashina cho'lning qoq o'rtasida uchrashdi (S. N.).* – KB, + A + H + A + T + A + E + H + K.

At last, on one beautiful day, a brave man and a powerful machine met in the middle of the desert.

4) Expresses the connection of the thought with the previous thought. To these demak (so), xullas (in short), xulosa qilib aytganda (in conclusion), anglashiladiki (it is understood that), shunday qilib (so), baribir (anyway), binobarin (consequently), ko'rinadiki (it seems that), ochiq qilib aytganda (to put it bluntly), qisqasi (in short), bir so'z bilan aytganda and etc: *Shunday qilib, tarixiy shartnomaga qo'l qo'yildi (Ya.).* – KB, + A + T + K.

Thus, the historical contract was signed.

5) It means that the thought being expressed is a commonly occurring event.

Odat bo'yicha, shovqin solish, atrofdagilarni bezovta qilish, asabiga tegish man qilinadi.
– KB, + E + E + E + K.

According to custom, it is forbidden to make noise, disturb others, touch their nerves

Some of the introductory structures (such as really, fortunately, right) are more likely to occur at the beginning of a sentence, some (seemingly) at the end of a sentence, and most in the middle of a sentence.

Input structures provide additional comments and information about the content of the sentence or the meaning of some of its parts. These are included in the sentence in the speech process and enter into a logical-semantic relationship with the sentence. Introductory structures have intonation independence. They are not an answer to a question, do not perform a syntactic function, do not become part of a sentence or part of a compound sentence.

Input structures explain the meaning of difficult or incomprehensible words (dialectism, professionalism, term, jargonism, archaism, historicism, etc.), the pronunciation and etymology of some lexical units, express the subjective-emotional attitude of the speaker, identify the source of the message. serves to display, provide additional information:

Boshidagi qalampir nusxa qora do'ppisi ham (na chust nusxaga o'xshaydi, na marg'ilon nusxaga) yangi (H. G'). – H + A + E + (KB) + OK.

Input structures are divided into 3 types according to their structure:

introductory part, introductory compound, introductory sentences. The input fragment is in the form of some words:

Go'daklikdan she'r yod ola boshlagan Alisher ajoyib natijaga erishdi. - H + T + A + E + A + T + K.

Alisher, who started memorizing poetry since childhood, achieved excellent results. *Ellik ming bayt (yuz ming satr) she'rni yod oldi (I. S.)* – H + T + FK.

He memorized fifty thousand verses (one hundred thousand lines)

Input compounds are in the form of a word combination:

U (safardan qaytgan kishi) ... juda mayda odatiy voqealarni ham qoldirmay so'zlar edi (G'.G'). – E + (KB) + ... H + A + A + T + H + FK.

He (the person who returned from the trip) used to talk without leaving out even the smallest ordinary events.

Introductory sentences are in the form of sentences: *At that moment, an old beg with a black beard riding a horse with a short tail (his face was hairless like a woman's, so the warriors called him "Kosa" among themselves) came running to Husayn. (L.B.)*. – H + A + A + A + A + E + (KB) + H + H + FK.

Introductory structures can occur in all types of sentences. Sometimes one sentence (more complex sentences) can contain several: *Mehmonxonaga joylashib, soqol – mo'ylovlarni olib (Ochil sho'x harakat bilan yuzini siladi), keyin agitator sifatida (u ko'kragini kerdi) salobat bilan kirib bordim (P.Q.)*. – H + T + H + (KB) + H + (KB) + H + FK.

Settled in the hotel, took a beard and mustache (Ochil rubs his face with a playful movement), then I entered with dignity as an agitator.

Summary. Although both languages have prepositional units, adverbial and conjunctive clauses, according to some sayings in the Uzbek language, prepositional units such as "he heard" are equal to the content of units in the English sentence (It is said that) and Uzbek We witnessed that sentences with multiple clauses (He washed his hands, undressed and ate.) in English form multiple clause models. Differences in these languages are clearly visible only in the modes of the sentence, and the sentences are considered to have a common content.

REFERENCES

1. Sayfullaeva R., Mengliev B., Boqiev G., Qurbonova M., Yunusova Z., Abuzalova M. Current Uzbek literary language- T.: Science and technology, 2009.
2. M. Kurbanova. Modern Uzbek language (Materials for the syntax of simple sentences). - Tashkent, - 2002.
3. U. Hoshimov. Inscriptions on the border of the notebook. - Tashkent, 2016.
4. Mukhtar. To my young friends. - Tashkent, - 1980.
5. P. Kadirov. Starry nights. - Tashkent, - 2016.
6. H. Tokhtaboev. Where are you, my child? - Tashkent, - 2017.